

Original Research Article

Autophagy is involved in granulosa cell death and follicular atresia in ewe ovaries

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ABSTRACT

In mammalian ovaries, most follicles do not ovulate and are eliminated by atresia, which primarily depends on granulosa cell (GC) apoptosis. Autophagy is an alternative mechanism involved in follicle depletion in mammals through independent or tandem action with apoptosis. However, follicular autophagy has not yet been investigated in sheep; therefore, the present study aimed to investigate the involvement of autophagy in atresia among a pool of growing antral follicles in ewe ovaries. The abundance of the autophagic marker LC3B-II was determined using western blotting in GCs collected from ewe antral follicles. The antral follicles were classified as healthy or atretic based on morphological criteria and steroid measurements in follicular fluid (FF). Immunofluorescence and confocal microscopy analyses were performed on GCs to evaluate the presence of autophagic proteins and their subcellular localisation. Caspase-3 and DNA fragmentation were assessed using western blotting and TUNEL assays, respectively, in the same GC population to investigate the simultaneous apoptosis. The novel results of this study demonstrated enhanced LC3B-II protein expression in GCs of atretic follicles compared to that of healthy ones (1.3-fold increase; $P = 0.0001$, ANOVA), indicating a correlation between autophagy enhancement in GCs and antral follicular atresia. Autophagy, either functioning independently or in tandem with apoptosis, may be involved in the atresia of growing antral follicles in ewe ovaries because atretic GCs also showed high levels of apoptotic markers. The findings of this study might have important implication on scientific understanding of ovarian follicle dynamics.

1. Introduction

Ovarian cell death is critical for homeostasis. Because most follicles are removed before ovulation via a degenerative process known as atresia, the percentage of follicle use is extremely low in mammalian ovaries [1,2]. Cows and sheep have approximately one million follicles in their ovaries at birth; however, over 95 % of these follicles undergo atresia at some stage of follicular development. Follicular atresia is a complex process that occurs at all folliculogenesis stages and involves multiple regulatory factors. In large mammals, including sheep, cattle, and humans, an increase in FSH levels during the follicular phase of the oestrus cycle leads to gonadotropin-dependent follicles (follicle waves) from the pool of growing antral follicles. However, only one or a few follicles from this group become ovulated. Therefore, follicle selection is

a regulated process that determines which follicles will survive, grow, become dominant and eventually ovulate, or degenerate, primarily through atresia. Unlike in primordial follicles, in which the focal point of atresia is the oocyte, the focal point of atresia in growing follicles is the death of granulosa cells (GCs) via apoptosis [2–5]. Large volumes of GC apoptosis within the granulosa membrane lead to follicular death.

Recently, the role of autophagy, a different mechanism of programmed cell death, has been demonstrated in ovarian GCs [6–8]. In eukaryotes, autophagy is essential for maintaining cellular homeostasis and is involved in several mechanisms, such as the disassembly of unnecessary or dysfunctional cell components, bacterial and viral degradation, and recycling of cellular components for cell metabolism. In addition to its pro-survival role, autophagy can also act as a pro-death mechanism under different conditions and cell types [9]. LC3B is the

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most studied and characterised isoform of the microtubule-associated protein 1A/1B-light chain 3 (LC3) family and plays a crucial role in autophagosome formation [10]. The relative abundance of membrane-bound LC3B-II correlates with the extent of autophagosome formation, making it a widely used and reliable marker for monitoring autophagic activity.

The role of autophagy in ovarian cell death has been previously documented in rodents [6,11], humans [12–14], and pigs [15]. However, reports on other mammalian species are scarce [16], and the possible involvement of autophagy in follicular selection for survival or degeneration in sheep has not been investigated. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the abundance and subcellular localisation of LC3B in GCs of healthy or atretic sheep antral follicles. Moreover, active caspase-3 protein expression and DNA fragmentation were analysed in the same pool of GCs to assess the occurrence of apoptosis in follicles undergoing atresia and the possible involvement of both processes in regulating GC death and antral follicle degeneration in ewe ovaries.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents

All reagents were procured from Sigma-Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA), unless otherwise stated.

2.2. Ovary collection and follicle classification

A total of 90 follicles from 40 ewes were recovered and used to collect follicular fluid (FF) and GCs. Ovaries were collected from adult non-pregnant ewes at a local slaughterhouse during the breeding season and transported within 1 h to the laboratory. The ovaries were then rinsed in a sterile, balanced salt solution of Dulbecco's PBS. Antral follicles were individually dissected free from the stroma under a stereomicroscope as previously described with slight modifications [10], and their diameters were recorded to an accuracy of 1 mm. Follicles of 3–5 mm in diameter were selected and classified into three groups according to validated morphological criteria [3,178,189]: healthy follicles (H) appeared well-vascularised, translucent, with compact GCs, and without any debris floating in the clear FF; early atretic follicles (A+) appeared quite opalescent, with little vascularisation, and some floating debris inside the FF; advanced atretic follicles (A+++), were opaque, with little to no vascularisation, and much debris floating in the FF. The follicles that did not fit into any of the groups were discarded. In addition to the above morphological evaluation, follicle health was assessed by measuring steroid hormone levels in FF.

2.3. Collecting follicular fluid and granulosa cells

Follicular fluid was individually aspirated from 30 follicles in each experimental group, separated from the cumulus–oocyte complex, and isolated from the GCs using centrifugation at $300\times g$ for 5 min. Because of the limited volume of each follicle sample, pools of three FF were created from H, A+, and A+++ follicles of small diameter to reach volumes over 50–60 μL . Ten samples were obtained from each category and stored at -80°C until steroid hormone analysis.

After FF aspiration, each follicular wall was placed in a culture dish containing sterile Dulbecco's PBS and hemisected using watchmaker forceps. When still attached to the follicle wall, the cumulus–oocyte complex was released into the dissection medium by scraping the inner surface of each follicle with forceps, which was removed with a Pasteur pipette. GCs were harvested by gently scraping the follicular wall with a spatula, transferred into individual 1.5-mL centrifuge tubes, and centrifuged at $300\times g$ for 5 min at 25°C to protect the cells from method-induced apoptosis. After removing the supernatant, GCs were briefly washed for 5 min with an ammonium chloride solution (0.155 mol/L NH_4Cl , 0.1 mM Na_2EDTA , and 0.01 mol/L KHCO_3) to eliminate

erythrocytes that contaminate GC samples from highly vascularised follicles [13]. Finally, another wash was performed with Dulbecco's PBS.

For each experimental group, the GC samples comprised GCs recovered from FF centrifugation and scraping of follicular walls (30 follicles) and were used to perform autophagy and apoptosis analyses (Fig. 1).

2.4. Hormone analyses

Steroid concentrations in FF samples were measured using radioimmunoassay (RIA) procedures [19,20]. Oestradiol (E2) was extracted from 10 μL of FF using diethyl ether, and the concentrations were determined using a solid-phase microtitre RIA. The antiserum, produced in a rabbit to 17β -estradiol (E2-6(O-carboxymethyl)-oxime-BSA (Lot 1; University of Udine, Udine, Italy), was used at a dilution of 1:40000. The cross-reactivities of the anti- 17β -estradiol antibody with other steroids were as follows: 17β -estradiol, 100 %; oestrone, 2.5 %; oestriol, 0.12 %; 17β -estradiol-(B-D-glucuronide), 0.04 %; 17β -estradiol-3-sulfate 0.012 %; DHEA, 0.007 %; 17α -estradiol, <0.04 %; progesterone, <0.04 %; testosterone, <0.04 %; androstenedione, <0.04 %; and estrone-3-sulfate, <0.04 %. Intra- and interassay coefficients of variation were 7.2 % and 10.7 %, respectively. The sensitivity of the assay was 1.84 pg/mL.

For progesterone (P4) evaluation, P4 was extracted from 10 μL of FF using petroleum ether and the concentrations were determined using a solid-phase microtitre RIA. The antiserum, produced in a rabbit to progesterone-11 α -hemisuccinate-BSA (Lot RA/13; Analytical Antibodies, Bologna, Italy), was used at a dilution of 1:8000. The cross-reactivities of the antiprogestosterone antibody with other steroids were as follows: progesterone, 100 %, 11 β -OH-progesterone 46 %; 17α -OH-progesterone, 0.4 %; 20 α -OH-progesterone, 0.04 %; testosterone, 0.08 %; cortisol, <0.01 %; estradiol- 17β , <0.01 %; estradiol- 17α , <0.01 %; and oestrone, <0.01 %. Intra- and interassay coefficients of variation were 6.9 % and 10.1 %, respectively. The sensitivity of the assay sensitivity was 10.8 pg/mL.

2.5. Granulosa cell culture

Granulosa cells were harvested from healthy and atretic antral follicles as described above. Granulosa cell viability was tested using trypan blue staining, and 5×10^4 viable cells were seeded in a sterile 8-well chambered cover glass containing 0.5 mL Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Medium (Gibco, Carlsbad, CA, USA) supplemented with 10 % foetal bovine serum and 0.5 % gentamicin solution.

Granulosa cells were cultured overnight at 38.5°C under a humidified atmosphere of 5 % CO_2 to allow cell adhesion. The next day, the cells were washed with PBS, fixed in 4 % paraformaldehyde, and processed for immunofluorescence (IF) analysis. A group of healthy GCs was treated for 1 h with 1 μM rapamycin solution (Abcam, Cambridge, UK; ab120224) before fixation to induce autophagy chemically.

2.6. Immunofluorescence staining

For LC3 immunostaining, GCs were washed twice with PBS after fixation, permeabilised with 0.2 % Triton X-100 in PBS for 30 min at room temperature, and washed twice with PBS +0.05 % Tween20 (PBST). Nonspecific binding sites were blocked using PBS +0.05 % Tween20 + 1 % BSA +20 % goat serum for 1 h at room temperature. The cells were then incubated with the rabbit polyclonal primary antibody against LC3B (1 mg/mL; Abcam, 48394) diluted to 1:100 in PBST overnight at 4°C in a humidified chamber. Negative control samples were incubated under the same conditions, but the primary antibody was omitted. The next day, after washing twice with PBST, the cells were incubated with the secondary Alexa Fluor 546 goat anti-rabbit antibody (Invitrogen, Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) diluted to

Fig. 1. Experimental design.

1:1000 in PBST. The cells were then washed twice with PBST, and nuclei were counterstained with 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ Hoechst 33342. After two consecutive washes, the coverslips containing the cultured cells were mounted on slides using the ProLong Gold antifade reagent (Invitrogen) and observed under a confocal microscope. Cell counting was performed by evaluating at least ten randomly selected fields in each group, with four replicates to quantify the number of autophagic GCs (LC3B-II positive).

2.7. Confocal microscopy analysis

Fluorescent images were acquired with a $60\times$ oil-immersion objective using a laser-scanning confocal microscope (Nikon A1r, Tokyo, Japan). A 488-nm line excitation of an air-cooled 100 mW argon laser (Spectra-Physics) was used, and the emitted fluorescence was detected using the appropriate AG2 filter set with a high pass at 561 nm. Images were captured using the NIS ELEMENTS 4.40 program in a section of 1024 pixels with zoom. The pixel size was 0,21 $\mu\text{m}/\text{px}$, and the pinhole aperture was 35,76.

2.8. Western blotting for LC3B detection

Granulosa cells were analysed to determine the amount of LC3B-I protein converted to LC3B-II, which is an index of autophagic induction. Cells collected as previously described were stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until western blotting (WB) analysis. The cells were lysed with RIPA lysis buffer supplemented with a protease inhibitor cocktail to obtain proteins. The mixture was then centrifuged at $12000\times g$ for 20 min at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and the supernatant was transferred into a 1.5-mL Eppendorf tube. The total protein concentration was biochemically determined, and the same amount of protein (20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{lane}$) was loaded for SDS-PAGE, followed by transfer to a polyvinylidene difluoride (PVDF) membrane. The membrane was then blocked for 1 h in 5% BSA and exposed to primary antibodies against LC3B (1:1000; Abcam; ab48394) and β -tubulin (1:1000; Santa Cruz Biotechnology, Dallas, TX, USA; sc-23949) at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

overnight. The next day, secondary antibodies, goat anti-mouse IgG horseradish peroxidase-conjugated secondary antibody (HRP)-conjugate (1:10000; Santa Cruz Biotechnology; sc-2005) and goat anti-rabbit HRP-conjugate (1:10000; Santa Cruz Biotechnology; sc-2030), were blotted to detect the corresponding bands using an Azure Imaging System C400 (Azure Biosystems, Dublin, CA, USA). The LC3B protein abundances were quantified by normalising the lipidated isoform of the protein (LC3B-II) against β -tubulin, and each band was imaged using ImageJ software (version 1.53; National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA).

2.9. Evaluating apoptosis in granulosa cells using WB for caspase-3

WB was performed as described above to quantify the active caspase-3 protein levels in H, A+, and A+++ GCs. For these analyses, the same protein samples obtained from GC lysis were subjected to SDS-PAGE. Separated proteins were electrotransferred onto PVDF membranes. After the nonspecific binding sites were blocked for 1 h in 5% BSA, the membrane was exposed to primary antibodies against caspase-3 (1:5000; MyBioSource; MBS565717) and β -tubulin (1:1000; Santa Cruz Biotechnology; sc-23949) overnight. The next day, the membrane was incubated for 1 h with secondary antibody goat anti-mouse IgG HRP-conjugate (1:10000; Santa Cruz Biotechnology; sc-2005). Specific bands were visualised using enhanced chemiluminescence using an Azure Imaging System (Azure Biosystems). Relative protein levels were calculated compared to the β -tubulin standard, and each band was imaged with ImageJ software.

2.10. Evaluating apoptosis in granulosa cells using the TUNEL assay

Late apoptosis was detected via DNA fragmentation in each group of GCs using the TUNEL assay with the ApopTag® Fluorescein Direct In Situ Apoptosis Detection Kit (Millipore, Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, after fixation, cells

were washed in PBS before being resuspended in an Equilibration Buffer and then in working strength TdT enzyme in a water bath for 30 min at 37 °C. The cells were incubated with a working strength Fluorescein Antibody solution for 30 min at room temperature, and propidium iodide staining solution (PI) was added for DNA staining.

The samples were then analysed using a CytoFLEX flow cytometer with 488 and 638 nm wavelength lasers (B53013) and CytExpert software (Beckman Coulter, Brea, CA, USA). Events were acquired by excitation with a 488 nm laser light and using band passes of 525/40 nm for ApopTag and 610/20 nm for PI. ApopTag-positive events indicated apoptotic cells, whereas PI-positive events and ApopTag-PI copositivity indicated necrotic cells. The flow rate was adjusted to 100–150 events/s, and 10,000 events were acquired for each independent sample.

2.11. Statistical analyses

All data are representative of at least three independent experiments (with comparable results). The statistical significance of the data was evaluated using ANOVA. Differences with values of $P < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1. Estradiol and progesterone content in FF

Healthy follicles showed higher concentrations of E2 in the FF than the A+ and A+++ follicles, regardless of follicle diameter (Table 1). An E2/P4 > 1 ratio was detected in H follicles, whereas A+ and A+++ follicles had an E2/P4 ratio < 1 (Table 1 and Fig. 2), indicating a strong correlation with the morphological classification of atresia.

3.2. Immunofluorescence analysis of LC3B in GCs

Confocal microscopy analysis revealed a widespread fluorescence signal in all GCs (Fig. 3), indicating that the LC3B protein was expressed in these cells regardless of the follicular status. However, GCs treated with rapamycin, an autophagy inducer (positive control, Fig. 3B), and most GCs of atretic follicles (Fig. 3D and E) showed cytoplasmic punctate fluorescence typically associated with cells undergoing enhanced autophagy.

When comparing the incidence of autophagic cells (GCs showing punctate fluorescence), the healthy group showed a lower percentage than the atretic groups, and no difference was observed at early or late-stage atresia (healthy = $51.8 \pm 12.6\%$, A+ = $86 \pm 2.2\%$, A+++ = $90 \pm 6.2\%$; $P < 0.0001$). However, in the GC population collected from follicles in the advanced stages of atresia, an increased number of cells was observed with many cytoplasmic vacuoles (Fig. 3E), which is possibly transformed GCs within the membrane granulosa capable of phagocytosing degenerating cellular elements, including atretic bodies [21,22].

Table 1

Estradiol 17 β (E2) and Progesterone (P4) concentrations were measured using RIA procedures in follicular fluid collected from healthy (H), early atretic (A+), and advanced atretic (A+++) sheep follicles.

	H	A+	A+++
E2 (ng/mL)	50.07 ± 10.45^a	3.24 ± 0.63^b	2.16 ± 0.74^b
P4 (ng/mL)	52.69 ± 11.25^a	47.90 ± 10.02^a	50.01 ± 6.92^a
E2/P4 ratio	1.05 ± 0.25^a	0.08 ± 0.01^b	0.05 ± 0.02^b

Values are the mean \pm SEM. ANOVA comparing 10 samples of H, A+, and A+++ follicular fluid collected from follicles of 3–5 mm in diameter. Means in the same row without a common letter differ significantly ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. 2. Follicular fluid E2/P4 ratio in healthy or atretic antral follicles. Follicular fluid E2/P4 ratio was obtained from 10 samples for each experimental group (H, A+, A+++). Means without a common letter differ, $P < 0.05$. H, healthy follicles; A+, early atretic follicles; A+++ advanced atretic sheep follicles.

3.3. WB analysis of LC3B and active caspase in GCs

Two distinct bands were visible on the blots at approximately 19 and 17 kDa, representing the cytosolic (LC3B-I) and lipidated (LC3B-II) forms of the protein, respectively (Fig. 4A). These bands are commonly observed when autophagy is triggered. An increase in LC3B-II protein levels in the GCs of atretic antral follicles was observed compared to H follicles (1.36- and 1.32-fold increase in A+ and A+++ vs. H group, respectively; $P < 0.0001$) (Fig. 4B). Furthermore, comparing LC3B-II protein levels in the two groups of atretic GCs confirmed the IF findings. The results indicated that autophagy is enhanced during the early stage of atresia and then maintained without a progressive increase throughout follicular atresia.

Cleaved caspase-3 expression in early and advanced atretic GCs was higher than that in healthy GCs ($P < 0.05$) (Fig. 5), demonstrating an active apoptotic cascade in the atretic groups.

3.4. Detecting apoptosis in GCs using the TUNEL assay and flow cytometry analysis

Flow cytometry results of GCs from healthy and atretic follicles indicated that there was a greater amount of DNA fragmentation (ApopTag-positive cells) in A+ and A+++ GCs than in H GCs (Fig. 6A). In particular, the percentage of ApopTag-positive cells was 65.33 ± 3.18 , 87.33 ± 0.88 , and 88.33 ± 1.76 in H, A+, and A+++ , respectively ($P < 0.05$; Fig. 6B).

4. Discussion

Follicle maturation and cyclic recruitment of the dominant follicle govern the ovulation rate in humans and animals, including sheep [23, 24]. In ewe ovaries, three or four follicular waves occur during each oestrus cycle. During each wave, antral follicles emerge from a pool of 2–3 mm follicles and grow to ≥ 5 mm in diameter before their regression or ovulation. Follicular atresia is a particularly crucial process in ewe ovaries, and an atresia percentage of >80 % is associated with the development of large oestrogenic follicles during the oestrus cycle [25]. Follicular atresia results from an imbalance between cell proliferation and death. Death within GCs is an integral part of normal follicular development when it occurs at a low prevalence; however, the follicle degenerates when a large volume of GC death occurs within the granulosa membrane. Atresia is a complex process involving multiple regulatory factors. In ewes, atresia of follicles of 3 mm in diameter is associated with a decrease in aromatase activity in GCs, follicular synthesis of cAMP in response to FSH and LH, concentrations of estradiol-17- β (E2) in FF [26–28], and the population of GCs [22,29].

Apoptosis is involved in GC death during follicular atresia in

Fig. 3. Immunofluorescence analysis of the LC3B protein in ovine granulosa cells (GCs) of healthy and atretic antral follicles. (A) Negative control without primary antibody. GCs immunostained with primary LC3B antibody, secondary Alexa Fluor 546 antibody (red fluorescence), and counterstained with Hoechst 33342 (blue fluorescence). All groups had the LC3B protein; however, a different abundance of LC3B-II-positive cells (undergoing induced autophagy) was detected. Most healthy GCs (C) had a diffused fluorescence without fluorescent puncta. Rapamycin-treated cells (positive control, B) and most early (D) and advanced (E) atretic cells had the typical punctate fluorescence pattern (arrows mark examples) associated with the LC3B-II protein in the autophagosomal membrane. In advanced atresia (E), many phagocytic cells with large cytoplasmic vacuoles and large dimensions were observed. Scale bars: 10 μ m.

mammalian species [2,3,5,30] and sheep [31–33]. However, the involvement of other cell death pathways in the ovaries is less established, and the cellular mechanisms responsible for the selection of follicles that degenerate or ovulate remain unclear and require further study [24,34]. Autophagy is involved in GC death during follicular development in humans [12–14], rodents [6,11], and pigs [15], suggesting an association between autophagy and follicular atresia. This study investigated the occurrence of autophagy in GCs of healthy or atretic growing antral follicles in sheep. E2 and P4 concentrations were measured in FF, which are standards for identifying follicle atresia to guarantee a reliable characterisation of the follicles, in addition to morphological evaluations that have been widely used in previous studies to assess the status of healthy follicles in domestic animals [3,15,35] and sheep [3,17,18]. Although the specific ratio between E2 and P4 varies depending on the species and detection method, higher E2 concentrations and a higher E2/P4 ratio indicate a healthy follicle status [36,37]; a previous study on ewe follicles suggested the same criteria

Fig. 4. LC3B protein content in GCs of healthy or atretic ewe follicles. (A) Immunoblotting was performed on equal amounts (20 μ g) of protein extracted from pools of GC of H, A+, and A+++ follicles. Two distinct bands were visible on the blots, located at approximately 19 and 17 kDa, representing LC3B-I and LC3B-II, respectively. Immunoblotting was performed using polyclonal anti-LC3B and anti- β -tubulin antibodies (upper) to normalise the results. (B) The data for the incidence of autophagic cells in GCs from healthy and atretic follicles are shown in the histogram. LC3B protein abundances were quantified by normalising the lipidated isoform of the protein (LC3B-II) against β -tubulin, and each band was imaged using ImageJ software. The values are expressed as fold increases over the mean densitometric content of LC3B-II in healthy GC.

[38]. In agreement with this, in the present study, steroid hormone concentrations in sheep FF showed higher E2 concentrations in healthy follicles than in atretic follicles. In addition, an E2/P4 ratio of >1 was detected in healthy follicles, whereas an E2/P4 ratio of <1 was detected in early and advanced atretic follicles. These results indicate a high correlation with the morphological criteria used in the present study to classify healthy and atretic follicles.

The results of the present study confirmed previous findings obtained in other species [6,15], demonstrating a large amount of LC3B immunoreactivity in sheep GCs during the antral stage of follicle development, regardless of the follicle health status. The LC3B protein is synthesised as a precursor called pro-LC3B, which must be processed into its cytosolic active form, LC3B-I. During autophagy initiation, LC3B-I is converted to LC3B-II, which is then recruited to the autophagosomal membranes. This study demonstrated a significantly higher percentage of LC3B-II positive cells in both atretic groups than in healthy follicles for the first time. These results suggest that autophagy is enhanced in the GCs of antral atretic follicles of 3–5 mm in diameter. Although phagocytic cells with several cytoplasmic vacuoles were more frequently identified in late atretic follicles than in the other follicles [21,22,39], LC3B-II immunoreactivity was not significantly different between early and advanced atretic GCs. These results demonstrate enhanced autophagy in sheep GCs at the early stage of atresia without a further significant increase during the late stage of follicular degeneration.

Western blotting demonstrated for the first time that the abundance of the LC3B-II protein was significantly higher in GCs harvested from

Fig. 5. Active caspase-3 protein content in GCs of healthy or atretic follicles. (A) Representative immunoblots were performed on equal amounts (20 μ g) of protein extracted from pools of GCs of H, A+, and A+++ sheep follicles. Immunoblotting was performed using polyclonal anti-caspase-3 and anti- β -tubulin antibodies to normalise the results. (B) The graph indicates the densitometric quantification of the active caspase-3. The values are expressed as a fold increase over the mean densitometric content of active caspase-3 in healthy GCs.

atretic follicles than in healthy GCs. Western blotting also indicated that autophagy in GCs already occurs at the early stage of atresia and is maintained during advanced atresia.

The apoptosis analyses and caspase-3 and TUNEL assay results are consistent with previous evidence in sheep [31–33], showing that apoptosis occurs in the GCs of antral atretic follicles during follicular degeneration. Notably, this study also performed apoptosis analyses using the same pools of healthy or atretic GCs used for autophagy analyses. Thus, this study demonstrated for the first time that enhanced autophagy and apoptosis simultaneously occur in the atretic GC population, with apoptosis and autophagy markers showing similar expression patterns during follicular atresia.

Therefore, in ewe ovaries, regulating GC death and antral follicle degeneration during the emergence of follicle waves from the pool of growing follicles may depend on the interplay between both programmed cell death processes—apoptosis and autophagy—rather than solely on apoptosis.

5. Conclusions

Autophagy, which functions either independently or in tandem with apoptosis, is involved in GC death and follicular atresia in ewe ovaries. The study findings might have important implication on scientific understanding of ovarian follicle dynamics. They highlight the complexity of follicular atresia, indicating that it is governed not just by apoptosis but also by autophagy. This dual mechanism may provide a more comprehensive understanding of the cellular and molecular processes involved in follicle turnover and ovarian function. Understanding the interplay between apoptosis and autophagy could reveal new insights into follicle transition from the growing pool to atresia, which is critical

Fig. 6. Analysis of DNA fragmentation in sheep GCs. (A) Representative overlay plot of flow cytometry depicting DNA fragmentation using the TUNEL assay in H, A+, and A+++ GCs. A shift towards the right on the x-axis indicates an increase in fluorescence intensity, whereas the y-axis indicates an increase in ApopTag-positive cells. (B) Bar diagram showing the percentage population of ApopTag-positive cells in H, A+, and A+++ GCs. Data are represented as the mean \pm SEM of three experiments. a, H vs. A+, $P = 0.0009$; b, H vs. A+++, $P = 0.0007$.

for maintaining ovarian health and function. However, further studies are necessary to elucidate the specific cause-effect relationship between autophagy and apoptosis.

Conflict of interests

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest regarding this work.

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Colour artwork

Colour should be used only in online version.

Data statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Aurora Scudieri: Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Luca Valbonetti:** Methodology, Investigation. **Tanja Peric:**

Investigation. **Alessio Cotticelli**: Investigation. **Marina Ramal-Sánchez**: Investigation. **Pasqualino Loi**: Resources, Funding acquisition. **Luisa Gioia**: Writing – original draft, Supervision, Resources, Investigation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

Declarations of interest: none.

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